

Republic of the Philippines

City of _____

S.S.

SWORN AFFIDAVIT OF DECLARATION

I, _____, of legal age, Filipino, [single/married], and resident of _____, Philippines, after having been duly sworn in accordance with the law, do hereby promised to do the following if elected as Mayor of _____ City:

The first ordinance that I will sign as City Mayor is the ordinance **ADOPTING** the Freedom of Information Ordinance of Pasig City with the title:

“AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.” (*Ordinance Number 37; Series of 2018; 12 pages*)

By adopting this ordinance, I commit to ensuring its full implementation and enforcement in accordance with its provisions.

I understand that transparency and accountability in governance are vital for the trust and welfare of the people, and I commit to upholding these principles through the enforcement of this ordinance.

In the first year of my term, I shall also prioritize the following ordinances:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|----------|
| 1. Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance | 4. _____ |
| 2. Anti-Epal Ordinance | 5. _____ |
| 3. _____ | 6. _____ |

As a commitment to my pledge, I **shall resign** as City Mayor if I fail to sign the above ordinances within the first year of my term.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, I have hereunto affixed my signature this ___ day of April, 2025 at _____.

Affiant

SUBSCRIBED AND SWORN to before me this ___ day of April 2025, at _____ Affiant exhibited to me his/her valid government-issued ID with the following details:

ID Type: _____
ID Number: _____

Doc. No.: _____
Page No.: _____
Book No.: _____
Series of **2025**

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS SWORN AFFIDAVIT OF DECLARATION

1. This document can be used by any elective officials with veto power such as Mayor, Governor, and President.
 - The term “City” can be changed to “Province” or “Philippines” respectively.
2. The first ordinance to be signed can be changed to any priority ordinance such as Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance, Anti-Epal Ordinance, or any Ordinance not yet passed in a specific Local Government Unit.
3. This Sworn Affidavit of Declaration can also be used by any Presidential Candidate. The Presidential Candidate can specify the list of his/her priority bills during the campaign period, as well as the very first Bill he/she will sign into Law. I published the below idea in one of my articles titled “The Tale of Two Leaders”.

Any President can use his power and position for the greater good.

Make a public or written declaration to the Congress:

"The first bill I will sign into law is the FOI Bill. I will never sign the General Appropriation Act (GAA) without a transparency mechanism in place for the more than ₱5 trillion budget.

I will veto the budget insertions of all senators and representatives who will not vote in favor of the FOI Bill."

Use the national budget as a strong leverage to pass landmark laws.

"We can either accept deception as normal, or we can try something new."

- Jonelle Peter Munoz (part of my article titled "Five seconds to end corruption and political dynasty - Will they Sign?)

4. *"In the first year of my term"* can be changed to *"In the first 100 days of my term"* or *"In the first n days of my term"*, where *n* is any integer greater than 0.
5. I only listed two priority ordinances, but any political candidate may list more than two. This document can evolve over the next few years to include infrastructure projects details, sectoral pie chart breakdowns, PPAs (projects, programs, and activities), financial and descriptive breakdowns of each PPA, and more—as part of the Affidavit's annexes.
6. Each ordinance and PPA budget/description can have its own specific annex.
7. The penalty can be changed to anything. The higher the penalty, the better. However, I don't think any other penalty is truly applicable to this kind of sworn affidavit. *Either deliver the campaign promise or resign.*

Five Seconds to End Corruption and Political Dynasty - Will they sign?

A contract has three important elements: a promise, an obligation, and a penalty.

A sworn affidavit, even though it is not a contract, can be used by any good politician to build trust and win votes.

A promise made during the campaign period.

An obligation to fulfill that promise.

A penalty in case the politician fails to deliver.

Benigno Aquino III promised to pass the Freedom of Information Bill into Law during the campaign period. However, after elected as President, he failed to prioritize the bill for six consecutive years.

Corruption has become the norm among many politicians. Good people become bad due to the lack of a transparency mechanism. Even the Vice President proudly announced in public:

"Napakaliit na amount ang P150 million. So bakit kami magnanakaw ng P150 million? Ang nakawan sa gobyerno ay bilyon-bilyon."

(P150 million is a very small amount. So why would we steal P150 million? Corruption in the government involves billions.)

There are 149 cities and 89 provinces in the Philippines. If each of them had a Freedom of Information Ordinance (or Local Law) with a penalty provision, it would be a powerful tool against corruption in the entire Philippines.

In 2018, Mayor Vico Sotto introduced a local FOI law in Pasig City with penalties:

1st Offense: Reprimand

2nd Offense: Suspension of five (5) to thirty (30) days

3rd Offense: Dismissal from service

"May ngipin ang lokal na batas."

Any local public official can be dismissed from office and lose their job if they fail to provide the requested document to the public.

Without corruption, we can have more funding for education, health, and other public services. All Filipinos can go to school without financial difficulties due to scholarships, and everyone can get the medical treatment they need without waiting for months or years.

This affidavit is an experiment—but one worth trying.

If it does not work, life moves on.

"Mabubudol na naman ang taumbayan ng mga politicians with empty promises."

But if it does work, it could be an unorthodox solution for passing the Freedom of Information Ordinance and other landmark laws in many cities and provinces.

"We can either accept deception as normal, or we can try something new."

The question to all Mayor and Governor Aspirants:

Will you sign this document in five seconds?

I can sign a document like this in five seconds. You can sign a document like this in five seconds. A good politician, to end broken promises, can sign a document like this in five seconds.

Even a blind Filipino, after hearing the FOI Ordinance of Mayor Vico Sotto, can sign this document in five seconds.

As a responsible Filipinos, we must demand from all politicians the highest standard of public service, transparency, and real accountability.

Elections only happen every three years. And there is a 45-day campaign period to sign a document like this in five seconds.

Kindly tag or send this document to any Mayor and Governor candidate. A wise person will act upon it.

The future is ours to change - let us start now.

Ipanalo natin ang Pilipinas !!!

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